

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

FENTON-TYPE HETEROGENEOUS OXIDATION OF PAPER MILL EFFLUENT IN BATCH AND CONTINUOUS REACTORS

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ABSTRACT

The application of heterogeneous Fenton-type systems was studied, using an industrial paper mill effluent and a model solution of sodium acetate. The reaction was investigated in a batch and a fixed bed reactor, at 70 °C. Different copper-based catalytic materials were supported on commercial spheres of gamma alumina. Besides, Zn, Fe, and Ce-containing catalysts were prepared and preliminarily tested for the acetate peroxidation, with comparative purposes. All the catalysts were calcined at 900 °C to improve the anchorage of active species on the support. For the experiments performed with acetate solution in the batch system with Cu²⁺/Al₂O₃ catalyst (C1 and C2), the TOC conversions were approximately 20%. With the industrial effluent, the TOC conversions were close to 45%, with leaching levels below 0.1 ppm Cu. In the continuous system, TOC reductions of the effluent were 20-30% after 4 h of operation. The decolorization degrees and oxidant consumptions were complete and the estimated reductions in aromatics content were near 70% (SUVA 254 nm), with a COD reduction of ca. 40%. The impact of two reaction parameters (oxidant concentration and residence time) was investigated, with a slightly positive effect.

Keywords: Heterogeneous Fenton, CuO/Al₂O₃, paper mill effluent, fixed bed reactor.

1. Introduction

Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOP) have been the subject of increasing research since the key work of Glaze et al., in 1987 [1]. The AOP group diverse techniques that take advantage of the high oxidation potential of hydroxyl radicals (HO•). These radicals can react with a large variety of pollutants, as arises from numerous studies and reviews in the field [2-12]. On this basis, the AOP are set as processes of choice for degrading recalcitrant contaminants [8]. Among catalytic AOP, Fenton oxidation processes combine simplicity and effectiveness, using available reactants (Fe²⁺ and H₂O₂) that are also easy to handle and environmentally benign. Classical Fenton oxidation has been widely investigated for the treatment of different wastewater streams, like paper mill effluents [13-17], and it was proposed as a “green” option for sludge conditioning and treatment [18]. More recent adaptations of the reaction system use heterogeneous species to activate the formation of HO• [10-11,19-20]; solid catalysts are preferred as they can be recovered by simple separation and reused [8]. Besides, selecting adequate catalytic material allows for overcoming some main drawbacks of Fenton oxidation, such as the narrow range of acidic pH requirements and the excessive sludge generation [11]. Most heterogeneous Fenton studies dealt with iron-based catalysts; however, other cations with multiple redox states (e.g., copper, cerium, chromium, ruthenium, cobalt) might directly decompose H₂O₂ into HO• through conventional Fenton-type pathways [7,21,22]. Non-ferrous systems have shown interesting results through a broader range of operational conditions [7-8]. It should be remarked that the hydrogen peroxide activation mechanism shows a specific dependence on the nature of the catalyst and its composition. In previous work, a summary of copper catalysts used for the degradation of recalcitrant organics was

presented [22-24] evaluating different reaction parameters for the CuO/Al₂O₃-H₂O₂ batch oxidation of effluents from the industrial alkaline sulfite treatment of wood (chemomechanical pulping). As these processes do not have a chemical recovery system, spent liquors are generally discharged into the receiving body. The wastewaters from the paper industry have a complex variety of chemical species, and several of its components are refractory to typical microbiological degradation and require more suitable technologies, as they are difficult to treat or to accomplish before discharge. Among the existing technologies, there are different AOP under study, such as ozonation, photocatalysis, classic Fenton, and heterogeneous Fenton-type oxidation [3-4,25-26].

To the present, there are a limited number of publications dealing with non-irradiated heterogeneous Fenton-like oxidation of industrial effluents (pulp bleaching, olive mill, pharmaceutical, textile, and tannery wastewater), mainly summarized in these reviews [20, 27-30]. Even fewer are the recent studies that applied copper-based catalysts for the continuous peroxidation of model pollutants [31-33]. Suraj et al. [34], synthesized a copper ferrite catalyst (using a co-precipitation method) and studied the oxidation of a pulp and paper effluent in a fixed bed laboratory scale reactor. The influence of process variables such as pH, concentration of H₂O₂, bed height and reaction time was optimized by analyzing statistical parameters. After 2 h of reaction time, about 78% chemical oxygen demand removal was achieved, with improved parameters. Catalyst reusability and stability was evaluated for four consecutive runs; the concentrations of Fe and Cu in treating effluent were below discharge limits.

The applicability of alumina supported catalysts in the peroxidation of wastewaters from the chemomechanical processing of biomass has been incipiently ex-

plored in batch reactors, with promising results. Covinich et al. [22] studied different homemade catalysts based on CuO, Fe₂O₃, NiO, and ZnO, supported on gamma-Al₂O₃ pellets (2.5 mm), for the catalytic oxidation of an industrial pulping effluent. The investigated variables were the hydrogen peroxide concentration, the catalyst loading, active species, and the reaction temperature. The best performance was registered using a CuO/Al₂O₃ system (chemical oxygen demand and total organic carbon reduction were between 40 and 50%, aromatic fraction reduction was >80% and the decolorization was 90%). In a further work, these authors [24] used CuO/Al₂O₃ pellets (1.8 mm), to conduct a kinetic study for the heterogeneous Fenton-type oxidation of mixed recalcitrant compounds in a real industrial effluent from the alkaline sulfite treatment of wood. TOC reductions near 50% were measured at 80 °C, using a lab-scale batch reaction system.

Based on this background, we set out to explore the application of CuO/Al₂O₃ catalysts at different operation conditions, to reduce the organic loading of effluent from the processing of biomass, using a fixed-bed continuous reactor. This offers a pathway towards more practical industrial application. In order to improve the anchorage of active species onto the solid support, a high calcination temperature was selected, according to di Luca et al. [35]. In the first instance, some preliminary batch-mode experiments were performed, using different active species impregnated over alumina spheres. From these results, further experiments were carried out to test the selected catalyst under continuous operation in a fixed bed reactor.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Reagents

The reagents used for the catalysts preparation were commercial spheres of gamma alumina (particle diameter=2.5 mm, Axens), Cu(NO₃)₂·2.5H₂O (p.a., Cicarelli), Ce(NO₃)₃ (Sigma Aldrich, pa) Zn(SO₄)·7H₂O (Riedel-de Haën, pa), citrate Fe(III) (BioPack, pa). For the catalytic tests and analytical determinations NaCH₃COO (p.a., Cicarelli), H₂O₂ (p.a., Cicarelli, 30%) and bidistilled water were used.

2.2. Preparation of the Cu²⁺/Al₂O₃ catalysts

Two different catalysts were prepared, using the commercial spheres of gamma Al₂O₃ as support. The impregnation solution consisted in cupric nitrate dissolved in bidistilled water. For catalyst C1, only one step of impregnation was used, followed by drying at 100 °C (12 h) and calcination in a muffle at 900 °C for 2 h (heating rate: 15 °C/min, under air atmosphere). In the case of the sample named C2, a similar amount of copper ions was loaded onto the support, but a two-step impregnation procedure was used. First, a certain mass of γAl₂O₃ was left in contact with an aqueous solution containing half the total amount of Cu²⁺. The wet solid was dried and calcined (at the same conditions than C1). Then, a second impregnation procedure was performed, with its subsequent drying and calcination stages.

In both catalyst samples the final copper content was similar, near 2% wt. of Cu species (2.5% wt. as CuO).

For comparative purposes, a third copper catalyst was prepared. The procedure was a one-step impregnation similar than for C1, but with twice the total copper content. This sample was named C1-4%.

2.3. Preparation of other catalyst systems

With the purpose of testing the behavior of a variety of active ions in the peroxidation of acetate species, the impregnation method was used to prepare different catalysts. The procedure was similar to the one described for catalyst C1. The samples obtained were: catalyst Fe₂O₃ (2.5%Fe₂O₃/γAl₂O₃); catalyst ZnO (2.5% ZnO/γAl₂O₃); catalyst CuO-Fe₂O₃ (1.25%CuO-1.25%Fe₂O₃/γAl₂O₃); catalyst CuO-CeO₂ (1.25%CuO-1.25%CeO₂/γAl₂O₃).

Two commercial catalysts were also included in this series of experiments. Catalyst “Engelhard” (ENGELHARD Cu0226S, 12.5% CuO-0.32% NiO) and catalyst “Topsoe” (TOPSOE LK821, 52% CuO-2% ZnO).

2.4. Catalyst Characterization techniques

The catalysts C1 and C2 were characterized by means of different techniques:

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD). The presence of different crystalline phases was determined using a PANalytical X’Pert Pro diffractometer, using CuKα radiation (1,54056 Å) and graphite monochromator at 40 kV and 40 mA (scanning speed: 0,02°/seg).

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). The surface morphology of the samples was determined using a Philips SEM 505, equipped with a EDAX DX APOLLO X probe to quantify Cu and Al surface contents.

Nitrogen physisorption. The measurement of particle surface areas and pore sizes were carried out by N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherm analysis at 77 K, using a Micromeritics Gemini 2380 equipment. The catalysts were ground and degassed at 150 °C (12 h).

Zero Charge Point (PZC). The pH value for zero charge of the solids was determined by the rapid titration method described by Mahmood et al. [36].

Copper content determination. The solid samples were mineralized using concentrated HNO₃, and a colorimetric method was used using CuVer ® reagent (HACH).

2.5. Reaction experiments

Two different target solutions were used. One is a liquor obtained from “Papel Prensa S.A” (San Pedro, Argentina), characterized elsewhere [22]. The effluent was a black liquor from the chemomechanical pulping; it was diluted (1:50), and the resultant initial COD and TOC were 931 and 433 mg/L, respectively; total dissolved solids were 1.2 g/L and sodium acetate content was 0.65 g/L. One of the major organic components of the effluent matrix is the acetate ion. So, parallel experiments were performed using a sodium acetate solution (1 g/L) as synthetic effluent, for the sake of comparison.

Batch reactor experiments. A PYREX glass batch reactor of 250 mL was used; it was equipped with a glass stopper, a condenser, a thermocouple, and a pH-meter. An agitation speed of 1000 rpm was selected to avoid mass transfer limitations. The experiments were performed at atmospheric pressure and 70 °C. The experimental set up was detailed in a previous work [22].

Heterogeneous experiments were conducted using catalyst spheres (5 g/L) in a reaction volume of 100 mL. Through all the catalytic tests, after the solution reached the desired temperature, the mass of catalyst sample was incorporated. Then the corresponding amount of oxidant agent was added (0.67- 1 mL; H₂O₂ 30%) to get an initial concentration of 0.12-0.24 mol/L. The addition of hydrogen peroxide was taken as the start of the reaction (t = 0 min). The experiments lasted 4 hours.

Fixed Bed Reactor experiments. A lab-scale fixed bed reactor (FBR) was also used, with an experimental setup similar to the one reported by [35]. The reactor consisted of a glass jacketed column (Internal diameter: 3 cm) operated at 70 °C. The catalyst load (25 g) was packed between inert glass spheres. The feed solution was pumped to the column in up-flow mode and the total flow rate was $Q_{liq} = 2.5-5.0$ mL/min. The oxidant initial dosage was adjusted between 0.12-0.18 mol/L.

The residence times of the liquid phase in the packed-bed reactor were calculated according to Martínez et al. [37].

Analytical methods. For both reaction systems, liquid samples were taken at adequate time intervals. The remaining concentration of oxidant was analyzed, pH, UV-VIS spectrum, and Total Organic Carbon (TOC) were determined (on filtered samples). For selected runs, also Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) was quantified.

At least three reaction experiments were carried out for each catalytic experiment. For the reported results, the coefficients of variation were in the range <4%.

H₂O₂ concentration was analyzed via standard iodometric titration, using KI and Na₂S₂O₃ 0.1 mol/L. TOC values were obtained using a TOC Analyzer (Shimadzu, TOC-VCPN model). The initial carbon mass

(or mass TOC_{initial}) was measured from a sample obtained prior H₂O₂ addition. COD was measured following the technique described in American Standard Test Methods [38]. Specific UV absorbance (SUVA) is defined as the UV absorbance of a water sample at a given wavelength normalized for dissolved organic carbon concentration. SUVA₂₅₄ values were obtained by dividing the UV absorbance (A) at $\lambda = 254$ nm by the organic carbon concentration (mg/L) [39]. Decolorization was also determined from visible absorbance measurements at 465 nm (Shimadzu Spectrophotometer).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of the fresh Cu²⁺/Al₂O₃ catalysts

By means of SEM analysis, irregular surface morphologies were detected, with comparable characteristics to the alumina support. For both C1 and C2 catalysts, active copper species were concentrated at the more external zones. For catalyst C2, the two successive impregnation-calcination steps gave rise to a more homogeneous distribution through the cross-section of the spheres (Fig. 1). EDAX results are the average from five measurements and confirmed the different active species distributions that could also be detected by visual examination of the samples. These results were consistent with the global Cu% determined by acid dissolution and colorimetric tests. Copper accumulation on the surface is expected due to the preparation procedure and the physical properties of the support (such as particle diameter, and density). A more prolonged thermal treatment could probably give samples with a more homogeneous concentration of copper cations on the support matrix; however, more direct and economical alternatives are studied at this stage.

Figure 1. SEM images of the cross section of fresh catalysts C1 and C2. For the positions 1-4 of the spheres cross-sections, the average Cu % wt. (EDAX) is shown.

No significant differences were observed between the XRD patterns of the catalysts and the alumina support (Figure 2). The comparison of the diffractograms for as-received and calcined gamma-Al₂O₃ was also included. Due to the low copper content incorporated and the relatively high surface area of the samples, it was expected that neither CuO nor

cupric aluminate phases were segregated. From these observations, it could be assumed that copper species are well-dispersed onto the alumina [40]. Alpha alumina characteristic peaks were not observed; when detected, the presence of alpha alumina could be indicating an anticipated transition of gamma phase, promoted by the presence of Cu ions [41].

Figure 2. XRD patterns for fresh catalysts C1 and C2, γ -Al₂O₃ (as-received); γ -Al₂O₃ calcined at 900 °C

The results obtained by N₂ physisorption are summarized in Table 1. The reduction in surface area and pore volume of the catalysts is consistent with the thermal treatment of the samples. The pore size distribution corresponded to mesoporous materials (the average pore size was near 15 nm for the catalysts and the calcined alumina). Catalyst C1 and alumina calcined at 900 °C showed similar results; no significant changes were induced by the presence of copper ions

in the support. This correlates with the previous mentions of cupric species being well-dispersed or incorporated in the framework of the alumina [42]. Stronger interactions between the active phase and the support promote the structural stability of the catalyst. In the case of catalyst C2, the surface area and pore volume reductions seem even more pronounced as two successive calcination steps at a high temperature were carried out.

Table 1.

Summary of characterization results for the support and fresh catalysts C1 and C2				
Sample	Cu content (% wt.)	BET Surface area (m ² /g)	Pore volume (cm ³ /g)	PZC (pH)
γ -Al ₂ O ₃	-	214	0.36	7.8
γ -Al ₂ O ₃ a 900°C	-	94	0.34	8.2
C1	2.0%	92	0.33	9.0
C2	2.1%	82	0.27	9.1

Table 1 also shows the pH determinations of the zero charge points. The catalysts registered PZC values that are above the circumneutral pH at which the reaction processes take place. Different authors have reported [43] that the efficiency of the oxidation process under these reaction conditions is strongly affected by the PZC of the catalyst and the pK_a of the contaminants studied. Below the PZC, the catalyst surface tends to be positively charged, favoring the interaction with anionic species in an aqueous solution, such as those investigated in the present study.

3.2. Reaction results

Batch reactor. Initial experiments were performed to investigate the peroxidation of model acetate solution. Figure 3 summarizes the final TOC and

H₂O₂ conversions in the batch reactor system at 70 °C. Different active phases were explored (Cu²⁺, Fe⁺³, Zn²⁺, Ni²⁺ and combinations). It can be observed that only a slight fraction of acetate ions (20% or below) could be mineralized by these Fenton-type systems, under mild conditions. Copper-based catalysts (selected from a previous work, [22]) could exhibit better performances than iron or zinc-based materials, as reported by different authors [7, 42]. This behavior is strongly associated to the lower potential of the Cu²⁺/Cu⁺ couple and the higher hydroxyl radical formation rates.

Figure 3. Sodium acetate degradation exploratory tests: TOC and hydrogen peroxide conversion percentages (after 4 h of reaction time), using different catalysts. Experimental conditions: $[\text{acetate}]_0 = 1 \text{ g/L}$; $[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]_0 = 0.12 \text{ mol/L}$; 5 g catalyst/L; 70 °C.

Short-chained organic acids exhibited good biodegradability in water. However, they affect the acidic properties of the aqueous medium and are refractory during chemical oxidation processes. Thus, they are frequently responsible of TOC abatement limitations of the wastewaters. These characteristics keep the organic

compounds such as acetate, out of the sight of advanced oxidation studies. Acetate ions are one of the most refractory and a main component of the organic loading of the black liquor. Thus, it was selected as target compound to conduct preliminary/comparative peroxidation studies.

Figure 4. a) TOC conversion and b) remnant H₂O₂ concentration for batch experiments performed with C1, C2 and C1-4% catalysts ("Ac", corresponds to sodium acetate solution, and "Ef", to the diluted black liquor). Experimental conditions: $[\text{H}_2\text{O}_2]_0 = 0.12 \text{ mol/L}$; 5 g catalyst/L; 70 °C.

Figure 4 exhibits reaction results (TOC conversion and remnant H₂O₂ concentration) for the batch experiments, using sodium acetate and the industrial

effluent. Table 2 summarized final TOC and H₂O₂ conversion, and pH values (after 4 h of reaction).

Reaction results after 4 h of reaction time in the batch reactor at 70 °C. Between parentheses, COD final percentage conversions.

Catalyst Sample	Target solution	TOC conversion (%)	H ₂ O ₂ conversion (%)	pH
γ -Al ₂ O ₃ 900°C	NaCH ₃ COO	3	<1	8.0
C1	NaCH ₃ COO	17	96	7.1
C2	NaCH ₃ COO	19	95	7.2
C1-4%	NaCH ₃ COO	13	100	7.8
γ -Al ₂ O ₃ 900°C	Industrial effluent	5	3	8.5
C1	Industrial effluent	41(48)	97	7.4
C2	Industrial effluent	43(49)	97	7.2
C1-4%	Industrial effluent	44(51)	100	8.1

As observed in Figure 4 b), there is an anomalous behavior in the profile of H₂O₂ consumption. Due to the high ratio of H₂O₂ decomposition for both catalysts C1 and C2, and additional dose of hydrogen peroxide was added to the system at 120 min. This addition corresponded to half of the total initial amount of oxidizing agent (the reaction volume was not significantly modified). The procedure allows the oxidation to continue, preventing the reaction from being stopped by depletion of the oxidant.

Some authors have estimated the H₂O₂ consumption efficiency [33-42] for peroxidation reactions. For the experiments reported in Figure 4, the efficiency was 7-10% (after 4 h of reaction), mainly due to the low TOC conversion levels. As previously mentioned, the activity of the copper species towards H₂O₂ decomposition was high, and complete consumption of the initial oxidant dose (after approximately 150 min) was registered (the remnant concentration of H₂O₂ after 4 h of reaction was <5% of the total two-step addition). However, from these observations, it is likely that an important amount of the added H₂O₂ participates in parasitic reactions, not only through HO• radicals formation [5,35]. This aspect is reported as one of the drawbacks of the application of copper-based heterogeneous Fenton-type systems, as more H₂O₂ is required to obtain high pollutant abatement (molecular oxygen disturbs the redox cycle, and part of the oxidant is lost during the process) [10]. However, as the high rate of oxidant decomposition promotes a complete depletion of the H₂O₂, the resultant solution does not need further destruction of the oxidant excess to be accomplished for discharge or subsequent treatment stages.

For catalyst C1-4%, a higher concentration of copper ions on the catalyst surface occurred (4.8% wt. Cu, according to average EDAX results), that also induced higher consumption rates of H₂O₂ (Fig. 5). Though, no marked increased in the TOC conversion were determined for catalyst C1-4%, compared to C1 and C2. Different causes might be considered: high consumption of oxidant through secondary reactions, rapid scavenging of HO• radicals, and/or less dispersed Cu species, that left relatively fewer active sites for the pollutant's oxidation [5, 32].

Blank experiments were also performed, in order to evaluate the incidence of adsorption processes (in the

absence of H₂O₂ oxidant, using C1 or Al₂O₃ support). Negligible variations in TOC determinations were registered. The conversion of acetate in the presence of H₂O₂ without catalyst was also insignificant (<1%).

Low leaching levels of copper ions (< 0,1 ppm) were confirmed during all the batch experiments. According to pH measurements, circumneutral conditions were maintained during the oxidation process, minimizing the solubilization of copper species. However, leaching could be also promoted by the presence of organic complexing agents. Based on the negligible concentration of copper ions in the final solution, a reinforced catalyst stability is confirmed, probably due to the good anchorage/strong interaction of copper ions in the support framework (promoted by the thermal treatment of the catalysts). Tentatively, four consecutive runs were performed reusing catalyst C1 in the presence of effluent (for a total of 16 hours). The conversions of TOC, H₂O₂, and the final pH of the reaction remained unchanged.

Although the liquor has a high initial loading of acetate ions (near 50% of the initial TOC could be associated to this species), the aqueous matrix contains other organic species that could be more easily oxidized than refractory acetate ions. Thus, as shown in Table 2, TOC conversions are higher for the industrial effluent. Complementary oxidation parameters of the wastewater were satisfactory: the black liquor was almost completely decolorized, 70% reduction of the aromatic fractions was registered, and 50% of COD removal after 4 h of reaction time. Regarding the H₂O₂ consumption, the time profile was comparable to that observed for model acetate solution. The initial dose of oxidant was completely consumed, and after 2 or 3 h of operation, an extra aliquot (+50%) of H₂O₂ was added. When the experiment finished, the remnant concentration of hydrogen peroxide was approximately 0.01 mol/L or lower.

So far, if the number of steps, the operation conditions and the reactants used during the treatment are to be taken into consideration, the experimental results seem promising, with a very positive respond to this non-irradiated Fenton-type oxidation process. Compared with previous results in batch mode, at 70 °C [22], similar conversion levels were reached in the present study. It should be noted that the prior adjustment

of optimized conditions might be now affected by the changes in the catalytic system. Although gamma alumina spheres were used in both works, the two supports have different textural properties. Frequently, throughout the scale-up, heterogeneous catalytic materials must be modified, as we pass from studies with powdered solids to studies with supported or pelletized systems. This process affects the physicochemical properties of the catalysts and their performances.

Fixed bed reactor. According to the results obtained using the batch reactor, no significant differences were found between C1 and C2 catalysts. Due to

the simplicity of the one step impregnation method, the following experiments in the continuous operation mode, were performed only with catalyst C1.

Figure 5 shows the temporal TOC conversion profiles for a typical experiment using the model acetate solution and the industrial effluent (for the latter, H_2O_2 conversion, $SUVA_{254}$ percentage reduction and pH were also presented). Based on preliminary tests, a final time of 240 min was selected for each run, in order to achieve pseudo steady-state conversions.

Figure 5. Conversion profiles vs time, in the FBR at 70 °C: TOC and H_2O_2 conversion, $SUVA_{254}$, pH evolution using the diluted black liquor (TOC conversion for the acetate solution was also shown). Experimental conditions: $[H_2O_2]_0 = 0.12 \text{ mol/L}$; $Q_{liq} = 2.5 \text{ mL/min}$; 70 °C.

For the experiments using acetate solution, the TOC conversions were between 10-18%, with complete depletion of the H_2O_2 during reaction (initial oxidant concentrations were between 0.12-0.24 mol/L). The impact of increasing the residence time and the oxidant dose was investigated, as summarized in Table 3. In the range of residence times tested, the impact of an increasing initial H_2O_2 concentration was minor. In general terms, very poor mineralization levels were achieved; however, both variables showed a positive

effect on TOC conversions. The solid/liquid ratio in this reactor configuration could be responsible of an even more rapid H_2O_2 decomposition through the catalytic bed. Thus, the slower acetate oxidation reaction could not be significantly improved when higher oxidant concentrations were used. A similar behavior might be inferred for increased residence times: if the oxidant is promptly depleted, longer residence times would not favor the acetate oxidation performance.

Table 3. Reaction results obtained at the FBR, at 70 °C, with catalyst C1 after 4 h of reaction. Between parentheses, COD final percentage conversions.

Target solution	Qliq (mL/min)	T (min)	$[H_2O_2]_0$ (mol/L)	TOC conversion (%)	Aromatics reduction (%)
NaCH ₃ COO	5	1,6	0.18	13	-
NaCH ₃ COO	5	1,6	0.12	10	-
NaCH ₃ COO	2.5	3,3	0.24	17	-
NaCH ₃ COO	2.5	3,3	0.12	10	-
Industrial effluent	5	1.6	0.18	19 (35)	67
Industrial effluent	5	1.6	0.12	15 (31)	62
Industrial effluent	2.5	3.3	0.18	21(39)	68
Industrial effluent	2.5	3.3	0.12	19 (34)	66

When the black liquor was used as target solution, the TOC conversions were in the range of 15-21%. TOC reduction levels were markedly lower than those reached during batch experiments. This is a common

observation when these two types of reaction systems are compared, due to their distinctive features (e.g., solid/liquid ratio, contact time between phases) [35].

FBR are attractive configurations that allow accelerating the oxidation of the organics and increases the treated volume of effluent by using shorter contact times. The main advantages over stirred-tank reactors are the well specified residence time, and fixed catalyst bed, which avoids separation of the solid catalyst and mechanical degradation. In our case, the higher solid/liquid ratio in the FBR, lead to relatively higher reduction in the aromatic fraction, estimated from SUVA₂₅₄. That is, with almost half of the “mineralization” conversions, the continuous process could give similar aromatics degradation than the batch mode. COD was also determined for some selected experiments with the industrial effluent, reaching near 40% of reduction. Complete decolorization was also obtained.

At constant residence time, a slightly positive effect of higher initial H₂O₂ dose was observed for the results obtained using the FBR. The changes in the reactor configuration parameters and residence time induce an increase in the conversion levels.

The maximum leached concentration of copper ions was far below the limit in Argentine legislation (1 ppm): 0.05 ppm for the experiments with higher initial concentration of H₂O₂ and 0.01 ppm for the experiments performed with 0.12 mol/L of H₂O₂.

The results obtained are satisfactory, so it is expected to advance the investigations to adjust the operative conditions to improve the levels of pollutants degradation, through simple and cost-effective strategies, with reduced environmental impact. The results support the hypothesis of the feasibility of the application of these treatment systems, as preliminary findings. The optimized operation conditions are not yet accomplished and must be adjusted. During the peroxidation process, the organic loading of the effluent was reduced, and the resultant parameters show good chances for further biological treatment. Toxicity tests and biodegradability tests are required to complete the final system characterization.

4. Conclusions

The use of Cu²⁺/Al₂O₃ catalysts in a heterogeneous Fenton process effectively reduced the organic load and aromatic content of industrial paper mill effluent, both in batch and fixed bed reactor configurations. The thermal treatment of catalytic materials allowed a good retention of active Cu species, reducing its leaching. The continuous reactor experiments highlight the possibility of treating larger effluent volumes, with a 70% removal of the aromatic content. The catalyst showed good stability and reusability in preliminary experiments. Further research will focus on optimizing process parameters and exploring the long-term stability of the system, as well as the costs and biodegradability of the final solutions, as this is a key parameter when a continuous industrial application is envisioned.

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